

The Impact of Business Factors on Weapons Trade from the US to Saudi Arabia

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Introduction

The imposition of arms embargoes can be done for a variety of reasons and by a variety of authorities, including international organizations (such as the United Nations (UN)), governments (such as the European Union (EU)), and even individual nations (such as the United States). According to the research, "weapons embargoes are one of the most often utilized types of economic penalties, but they are also believed to be one of the least successful." According to Moore, practically "every international arms embargo has been routinely broken by arms exporting powers," and that includes the United States. So what's the point of conducting yet another evaluation of its effectiveness? This chapter, which is based on the premise that arms embargoes ultimately seek to influence the behavior of the target (i.e., the country receiving the embargo), argues that another analysis of effectiveness may indeed be beneficial in some circumstances. A dashboard is being developed to evaluate the effectiveness of arms embargoes, based on literature⁴

ABSTRACT

The ongoing economic interactions between the United States and Saudi Arabia regarding the export of oil to the United States indicate that the relationship will only get stronger in the future. Consequently, the exportation of weapons between the two countries implies that the two countries are constantly striving to create favorable working environments in which the transactions might flourish, thereby increasing the volume of weapons traded between the two countries. At the end of the day, it is correct to assume that when countries have a positive relationship with one another, the likelihood of economic transactions between the two countries is secured. Countries that are tense or have poor relations with one another, on the other hand, suffer from unpleasant working conditions, which means they are unable to provide positive working environments for one another, ultimately resulting in little or no trade between the two economies.

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that has been used to determine success. In order to provide an example of how the dashboard might be used, we will use the arms embargo against Saudi Arabia, which was implemented in 2018 by a number of EU member states in response to this country's involvement in the Yemeni civil war, which has been waging since 2014.

Technology, ICT and Export of Weapons between the US and Saudi Arabia

Wahab and colleagues (2012) define technology in different terms according to the role technology plays at a particular time of definition. For instance, technology has been described from viewing it as having two primary parts, i.e., a physical element which has tangible products and equipment such as tools and a non-physical aspect that is strictly made up of information and skills in managing, producing, controlling, and providing reliability. On the other hand, technology can be defined as a configuration, whereby the transfer object, i.e., technology is subject to the pre-determined processes and products.

Technology can be directly linked to having and applying knowledge. Also, in addition to expertise, research, and development are vital in the definition and application of technology (Wahab et al., 2012). Therefore, technology is meant to obtain results, solve problems and overcome challenges, completing tasks, and exploiting the assets and resources available.

Through technological advancement in the US and Saudi Arabia, there has been a change in the way the two countries carry out arms exportation. There have been immense transformations experienced in how the countries organize their production process, conduct trade, and allocate the available capital. Additionally, there has been a change in the way the states carry out their operations and product creation (Muroyama & Stever, 1988). Through improved production techniques, the US has been able to improve on the previously practiced production techniques, hence producing more sophisticated ammunition and combat techniques that they export to Saudi Arabia. Also, improvement in air and water transportation through the use of technology has improved the speed of production and delivery of the weapons to the end-users.

Technology has also helped in the diversification of the products being delivered. Through innovation, there has been an improvement in how weapons are made in the US. Technology has enabled to use of old technology to create new weapons, make arms previously in the market using modern technology, and building entirely new products using the discovered technology (Ferragina & Pastor, 2007). Therefore, there is a broader range of weapons and combat techniques brought forward by the use of innovative technology and building on previous knowledge on weapon-production.

Furthermore, technology helps a country to remain competitive in their endeavors. As intimated by Marquez-Ramos and Martínez-Zarzoso (2010), a country's economic development is directly linked to its advancement in technology. Through technological advancement, the US has been able to enjoy lower production costs since they save on human resources, transportation, and communication fees. Additionally, through ICT, there is a reduction of barriers to communication since information is swiftly shared between the two trade partners without physical interaction. Through the infusion of technology in their production of weapons, the US has been able to be the major exporter of arms globally from 2015-2019, exporting 35% of the world's weapons (Varcellone, 2020). Therefore, through technology, the US has remained to be the go-to supplier for Saudi Arabia and the majority of the world's nations.

Finally, through the use of ICT, the US has been able to be more effective in their exportation of weapons to the US. Through the use of e-commerce, the two partners have been able to keep their business relationships and interactions going without the need for physical meetings by using the available means of telecommunication means. Also, through the internet, the two trade partners can conduct transactions and even offer training and other after-sale services on the

use of weapons. Xing (2018) states that the United States' use of telecommunication in their trade between 1975 and 2000 resulted in a 10% increase in internet usage in the country they transacted with, resulting in a 1% increase in the exports and imports between the trading partners. Therefore, not only does ICT ease communication, but it also improves the rates of adoption of technology between the interacting partners.

Demography and Export of Weapons between the US and Saudi Arabia

The demography of a country is defined as the population size and its composition. Additionally, critical attributes in demographic factors include the literacy levels of the people and the differences in the incomes of individuals in society. It can be theoretically stated that the larger the population of a country, the bigger the potential market for the goods produced. However, there are also other factors such as age and sex of the target market that play a role in the availability of a market for the finished products (ExportHelp, 2020).

Additionally, Harding (2009) states that the population changes experienced in the 21st Century do mean not only a difference in the distribution of people but also a difference in the flow of delivery of goods around the world. Factors such as having an aging population, migration, and immigration, and the inclusion of women in the labor force mean that countries' competitive advantage and stand in the world export business is different depending on the demographic structure of the said nation. It is also expected that countries with a younger population are bound to have a competitive advantage in manufacturing industries. This reality is advantageous to the US, which has a population of 191,499,600 people in the workforce out of a total of 318,498,500 total population (KFF, 2018). Therefore, the availability of an active workforce in the US makes the supply of weapons for export to Saudi Arabia possible.

The population structure in a country plays a part in the scale and structural effect on the bilateral relationship between the US and Saudi Arabia. Tian, Yao, Yu & Zhou (2011) define scale effect as the existence of a population which has an existing workforce in the country undertaking production, meaning that they can export a large volume of goods, while also providing a market for the importation of more products. On the other hand, the structural effect is the changes that a nation would experience should the number of a nation's workforce be affected positively or negatively. Therefore, changes in population size and structure in the US and Saudi Arabia will affect the number of weapons exported and imported, respectively.

Having an export-oriented strategy is aided by certain factors in the make-up of the population. Having a large amount of labor force, urbanization, and low dependency ratio is vital in ensuring that a country meets its goals in exporting on a large scale. Seeing that the US fulfills all the requirements for export orientation in its production process, a self-selection behavior is achieved in the process (Yao & Yu, 2009). A large number of work force provides an opportunity for the manufacturing industries to produce a surplus that caters to both the domestic needs and export needs, and the surplus offers for the supply of weapons to be exported to Saudi Arabia.

According to the ILO (2010), a skilled workforce in a country ensures the sustainability of the country and the global transactions it undertakes. Therefore, if the US has a skilled workforce, there will be more production of weapons ready for export to Saudi Arabia. Similarly, if Saudi Arabia trains its military personnel to handle the imported weapons, then there is a higher possibility of the nation importing more weapons from the US.

Natural Resources and Arms Export between the US and Saudi Arabia

Access and availability to energy are vital in ensuring the well-being of the society, nurture economic advancement, and fighting off poverty. However, there is a need for economies to ensure that a balance between the pursuit of industrial excellence and providing environmental protection is achieved. In the 1960s, the West (North America and Europe) was

the primary consumer of energy sources, mostly oil. However, contemporary times have seen a change in this trend. Other parts of the world, especially the Pacific regions, have seen at least a 12-fold increase in the consumption of energy resources. By 2015, the Pacific region was consuming energy equaling the intake of the energy consumed in Europe and North America (Ritchie & Roser, 2014). Coal has been overtaken by oil in recent years in terms of usage due to the efficiency of oil to coal.

Energy plays a critical role in the economic growth of a country. Industrialization heavily relies on the use of power, and if a country masters the efficient use of energy, then the country's success in manufacturing is assured. Population growth and the incessant search for economic prosperity by nations provide the continuous need for economies to seek efficient and reliable sources of energy (Erkan, Mucuk & Uysal, 2010). Energy consumption in the world grows parallel to economic and demographic advancement. Therefore, as the population increases and new technologies are discovered, then the need for more energy sources arises. Technology gives the US more innovations that need to be manufactured and brought to reality. Only a sustainable source of energy will ensure that the dreams are brought to life. Saudi Arabia is the second-largest producer of oil globally (Investopedia, 2019). While this is so, the nation is unable to use the energy they produce to produce the weaponry they need. On the other hand, the United States, which is the biggest producer of oil on earth, has mastered both the management and use of the oil that is abundant in their country. Therefore, by learning the production and management of energy, the US has been able to continually export weapons to Saudi Arabia and the world at large.

While the US is the world's largest producer of oil and natural gas, the country has been for the motion of using the energy domestically and store up the excess production. In recent years, there have been calls to relax the restrictions on the exportation of oil from the US because of the increased oil and gas deposits that have been found in the country (Arora, 2014). However, this approach by the US has been a secret for their success in mastering the international exportation business through intensifying production in their country. Additionally, the US' attitude has helped local manufacturing and production by ensuring that the energy prices remain affordable to all local manufactures. Therefore, they can undertake intensive output of arms and other industrial products.

The economic sustainability of a nation is tied to its commercial growth rates. This being so, economic growth is also directly linked to energy use in the country in terms of the intensity of the usage and the pricing of the energy source. Ergo, the more the energy consumption of a country is, the more the nation's GDP (Korsakienė, Tvaronavičienė & Smaliukienė, 2014). However, despite suspected expectations that increased energy prices affect the economic growth of a country, studies show that even despite increased energy prices, a country can still prosper. This is because the states can reflect these extra charges in the final pricing to the end-user. Therefore, due to the intensive use of energy in the manufacturing industry in the US ensures that the increasing energy costs do not deter their manufacturing and export missions, and this is reflected in the rising economic prosperity enjoyed by the US.

Following the initial oil shock of 1973, researchers have been interested in the impact of oil prices on oil-exporting countries. Alekhina & Yoshino (2010) state that an increase in production costs causes fluctuations in oil prices. With an increase in oil prices, oil-exporting countries like Saudi Arabia experience increased capital in the form of foreign currencies, and this reflects on an increase in the nation's GDP. With an increased GDP, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia can import more weapons from the US, and this causes a ripple effect on the improvement in the US' GDP and economy, respectively.

Finally, it should be noted that energy is critical in globalization and exportation in the world. Overland (2016) cites the Middle Eastern oil crisis of 1972, and the Russo-Ukrainian gas crisis of 2006, 2009, and 2014 to illustrate how dependent

the world is on energy. Had countries that import energy been self-sufficient during these times, then these crises would not have happened, and the world's economy would not have taken a blow in the process. Therefore, if the United States, which is an exporter of weapons to Saudi Arabia, would find a sustainable source of energy to help them in their production, there will be economic prosperity due to increased levels of production and exports. Additionally, sustainable energy sources mean that the energy is cheaper since it can be recycled and reused, compared to non-renewable energy use.

Exchange Rates and Weapons trade between the US and Saudi Arabia

There are direct and indirect links related to the effect of exchange rates on international trade. Direct links came to be a point of interest for scholars after the unexpected rise of exchange rates during the gold exchange standard (WTO, 2017). Exchange rates affect the economy directly since they affect the output of investment, change the allocation of external trading, influence the availability and cost of labor, and alter accounts held externally. Therefore, it can be concluded that exchange rates affect economies both directly and indirectly. However, the indirect links are hard to be substantiated, and this explains why exchange rates are treated independently as a shifting variable.

Exchange rates affect the economies directly and indirectly. Real exchange rates affect the allocation of resources and are used as a measure of competitiveness in an economy. Misalignment of exchange rates and inflation of prices leads to the setting of wrong prices for exported goods, in turn affecting international trade negatively. Also, it affects investment decision-making leading to a shift in the allocation of resources that may prove to be misinformed (WTO, 2017). Additionally, there are commercial risks associated with inflated exchange rates due to the uncertainty that arises during the period of inflation. The uncertainty on how long the inflation will be in place pushes prices further up, making the countries sourcing for goods through importation procure fewer products due to the devalued state of their currency. This being so, the number of arms exported to Saudi Arabia from the US is directly intertwined with the exchange rate of the Saudi Riyal against the US dollar.

With globalization, the world's economies are presented with business opportunities that they can exploit to achieve maximum profits. The opportunities presented include technological and innovative advancements, capital mobility, and investment opportunities. For this matter, economies need to develop a free-floating currency exchange system whereby the market value of the agreed-upon currency, i.e., the dollar, is determined by the forces of demand and supply in the international forex market (Ngondo & Khobai, 2018). Therefore, the United States and Saudi Arabia can decide to use the forces of demand and supply of weaponry in the international forex market to determine the price of the weaponry exported, hence ensuring that the demand of Saudi Arabia for weapons is not affected by the inflation rates. However, the free-floating currency exchange system can be argued to be both positive and harmful to the economies that decide to implement it. While it allows for mobility of capital across the globe, the variability brought about by the exchange rates voids the positive effects brought by the approach (Ngondo & Khobai, 2018). Therefore, the two countries can also decide to use the free-floating approach of exchange partially or on a case to case basis.

Economies have to devise ways in which to overcome the challenges posed by an unfavorable balance of payment, accumulated foreign debt, inflation levels, and slow growth rates. Some of the suggested tactics include the formulation of tactics that directly bring benefits and stabilization to the macroeconomic factors in the country. These factors include improving standards of living, liberalizing the economy, and championing economic freedom of the masses. More importantly, the adoption of a favorable exchange system regime should be considered to ensure that the nation undertaking the policies benefit from their selection. A country's decision on an exchange system regime depends on the country's size, past, sophistication, ease of doing business in the economy, and the major trade partners of the

economy (Nyambariga, 2017). Therefore, the exchange rates and exchange rates regimes in place both in the US and Saudi Arabia determines the number of arms that will be exchanged between the two economies. If the regimes are favorable, then the number of weapons exported between the two countries is increased, while an unfavorable exchange system will lead to lesser volumes of weapons exchanged.

Kass (2020) offers reasons for factors that affect the exchange rates between economies' currencies. First, the inflation rates of a country will determine the exchange rates. Countries experiencing low inflation rates experience a rising value of their currency against those that are experiencing high inflation rates. High inflation means that the amount of purchases is reduced, and therefore less trade is happening between the countries. Therefore, if Saudi Arabia experiences high inflation rates, it means that the number of weapons they import from the US will be reduced. On the other hand, if the US experiences a higher inflation rate than Saudi Arabia, then it means that Saudi Arabia will import higher volumes of weapons. Secondly, interest rates on borrowed funds determine the exchange rates. If a country borrows funds, the interest rates of the loan will determine the exchange rates. If it is found that a state pays more interest, there will be more lenders willing to give those loans and means that demand for the currency will rise, and this will increase the exchange rates. That being so, if the prices are less, there will be little demand for the money, and therefore exchange rates will plummet.

Additionally, current accounts that a country maintains determine exchange rates. Current accounts include the balance of trade and returns from investments made abroad. A deficit in the current accounts is arrived at when the country imports more than it exports. This deficit brings about depreciation in the currency, causing the currency exchange rates to be high (Kass, 2017). Furthermore, government debts can be a cause of increased or reduced exchange rates. If investors fear that their government has taken too many loans, they sell their previously-purchased bonds and investments, thus reducing the supply for the currency leading to a declined foreign exchange rate. This situation leads to a spike in inflation. In a different case, the prices of inflation go down when investors are confident in the way the loans that the government has taken and their debt management. In this situation, the investors will buy more government bonds and increase their investments in the economy, increasing the demand for the currency and hence strengthening the exchange rates of the currency.

The political and economic stability of an economy plays a part in the exchange rates of economies. Kass (2020) explains this point by describing how investors are more likely to invest in countries where there is political stability since the conditions there are predictable. Therefore, countries with political stability experience a more substantial exchange rate and consequently reduced inflation levels. Finally, the speculation by investors leads to increased inflation and exchange rates. If a country is set to experience recession, then investors will sell their investments at a loss resulting in a decline in the value of the currency.

GDP and the Arms Export between the US and Saudi Arabia

Shihab and colleagues (2014) argue that a country's economic welfare determines economic growth. Exports are a country's main source of foreign exchange, and they help create a balance of payment that is both favorable and has less pressure. Additionally, the exportation of goods and services by a country provides the nation's workforce with employment opportunities.

Therefore, it can be correctly concluded that if the US' GDP is high, then they will be able to support their manufacturing industries, hence provide more weaponry to satisfy the demand by Saudi Arabia. Additionally, if Saudi Arabia's GDP is high, it means that its purchasing power for weapons will be high, and therefore they will be able to buy more weapons from the US.

The US Bureau of Economic Analysis gives the US' growth rates as -0.92% in 2008, 3.88% in 2014, and 2.93% in 2015 (AKALPLER & SHAMADEEN, 2017). These economic growths were attributed to residential fixed and non-fixed investments, personal expenditures, and government expenditure. Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) has a direct role in an increase in economic growth, albeit slightly insignificant. Conclusively, there is a direct co-relationship between exports, economic growth, and an increase in a country's GDP.

There has been a debate on how significant role exports play in improving an economy's GDP, with a consensus yet to be reached. Despite the arguments, it is agreed that economic growth in every country's priority. Also, it agreed that economic growth is important for economic development to be achieved. There have been studies to show a direct link between exports and economic growth. Hameed & Devi (2012) attribute positive external factors to ensure the economy's success. Therefore, it can be concluded that if conditions in the Saudi market are positive, then the production of weapons in the US will be increased. This is because the positive reception of the weapons will provide positive financial motivation for the US to keep on manufacturing. Concerning this, if the oil Saudi Arabia produces is well-received to the countries they export to, then they will have the financial muscle to import more weapons from the US. GDP helps economies to improve the living standards of their people. An increase in GDP means economic growth for economies. Through the use of VAR analysis, Ronit & Divya (2014), a stable VAR chart means that there is a growth in exports, reflecting economic growth for the country under study. However, a large GDP does not necessarily mean that the economy will have more exports since the domestic demand will increase, and the products meant to be exported will be consumed locally. Ogbokor & Meyer (2017) tie economic growth to exports. The growth is mainly due to globalization of trade since technological advancement has made trading globally easier. Through the use of time series procedures, it is possible to see how an increase in exports aids an economy's GDP to grow.

Transportation and Weapons Export between the US and Saudi Arabia

When a nation invests in transportation, there is a reduced amount of money and time spent in the production and delivery period. Efficiency in transportation ensures that a country is both competitive in its participation in international trade. Albrarran ET. Al list transportation and transportation costs as an integral part of international business. Having efficient transport systems ensures that the cost of participating in international business is reduced, meaning more profits for the economy. The competitiveness is the ability of businesses and countries to deliver higher quality goods in shorter periods and at lower costs. Therefore, if the US is to maintain its competitiveness in exporting weapons globally, specifically to Saudi Arabia, then it means that they have to improve on their infrastructure. Also, if Saudi Arabia ensures that its transport network is well-established, then it means that the oil they export worldwide will be delivered promptly. With this, there will be more profits and, therefore, more financial power to import more weapons from the US.

Behar and Bernabes (2010) discuss the effect of transportation costs on the export business. They argue that when transportation costs are low, then the cost of production will go down, providing room for the production of more goods for export. Therefore, if the US can streamline its transport system, they can achieve maximum profits for the weapons they export to Saudi Arabia, and the case is the same for Saudi Arabia. If they have an efficient transport system, then their oil will be quickly transported to the countries it is to be exported, and the increased incomes will provide them with a chance to import more weapons from the US.

The importance of a road system has been stressed by Blyde (2010). By establishing a reliable road network in the respective countries, the production process is quickened, meaning that the product will be processed and transported to their destinations quickly. Therefore, if the US has a reliable road network, the production of weapons will be eased

since the raw materials can be swiftly transported to the respective factories to ensure that the international demand for weapons is addressed fast. Also, if Saudi Arabia's road network is good, it means that the imported weapons will be received and transported to the areas they are needed, in a timely and effective manner.

With the globalization of trade defining this era, it is also important to explore the effects of having an efficient transport system to support the practice. Globalization can't be without transportation (Ślusarczyk, 2010). This is because transportation ensures the movement of goods and people, creating a worldwide market in the process. The arms deal between the US and Saudi Arabia would be impossible to happen if there was the unavailability of a transport network connecting the US and Saudi Arabia.

Finally, transportation helps in facilitating trade, both local and international. Through the TFA agreements arrived at in Bali, 2013, policymakers showed the critical role played by transportation in ensuring international trade took place. Therefore, countries must ensure that they have an effective transport system and that their international trade partners do not struggle to deliver goods to them or having the goods supplied to them take too long or experience unnecessary hardships in the process.

Culture and its Role in the US Export of Weapons to Saudi Arabia

Culture is the way of life and how people carry out their day to day activities. Kalhor et al. define culture in different aspects. First, they define culture as concepts and beliefs that form a behavioral pattern of society. Secondly, they defined culture as the values and measures of values in a society. Finally, a more suitable and applicable definition was given to culture as a mixture of knowledge, beliefs, laws, traditional practices, and skills in the course of a society's interaction in their day to day interactions within themselves and with others.

Culture grows and evolves with time, and the negative aspects of culture may deter the development and improvement of commerce and economic growth. Kalhor et al. (2014) mention Gandhi's mention of the West's impact on the world's culture, with the western culture being responsible for eroding other cultures, human values, and converting human beings into machines only concerned with production and making money. Therefore, it can be concluded that cultures can be exchanged with continued trading interactions between economies.

Culture leads to economic development. Through the inclusion of culture into public policy-making, and co-operation of international development projects, economies can experience great strides in achieving great economic milestones and smother the export business globally. There have been steps made towards achieving cultural rights in international trade. Marana (2010) identifies the inherent need for incorporation of culture into development. Therefore, it is important for the US and Saudi Arabia to include their nations' cultures into their development programs and, more importantly, the export interactions between the two nations.

Culture and globalization go hand in hand. Globalization is the intensification of economic activities among different nations of the world (Globalization 101). There have been strong efforts by economies to protect themselves from the effects brought by globalization and the increased interaction between the world economies. Therefore, economies need to find ways to protect themselves from the negative effects of cultures brought into their countries as they interact with each other in trade. For example, Saudi Arabia is mostly a Muslim country guided by Muslim values, and therefore they are conservative. On the other hand, the US is mainly made up of liberal culture, and consequently, they are not conservative in their behavior. The interaction between the two nations has to be in such a way that the cultures of the two nations do not clash and that only the positive aspects of the two cultures are exchanged between them.

Finally, the economies of the world need to develop an export-oriented approach and culture for their economic development. Corporate culture has to be developed in that the structure, strategic planning, and daily operations in the

economy and also in their relationship with other countries. Having an export-oriented culture is important since it affects the decision-making of the economy, consequently affecting the performance of the economy (Navarro-Garcia ET. Al, 2013). The export-oriented culture of the US has enabled them to remain a world-renown exporter of weapons. On the other hand, Saudi Arabia has also developed an export-oriented approach in its oil production, and this has also made them develop into the world's largest supplier of oil. Therefore, the export-oriented culture of the two countries has helped the countries to provide for their needs, i.e., the US becoming the world's biggest weapons exporter, and Saudi Arabia getting enough money to procure weapons from the US.

Government Policies and Export of Weapons between the US and Saudi Arabia

Government policies affect how the production and export of goods and services. Admittedly, if the government policies are favorable to the trade, then there will be positive results emanating from the experience, and negative trade terms will result in negative results.

According to NES, Jamaica (2020), government policies are formulated to bring economic growth and ensure the sustainability of the methods of production. The policies are also meant to contribute to the economy's GDP by increasing the exports from within, increase the role of exportation in employing its population, and achieving more diversification of the economy.

Diversification is achieved by setting up more policies that will enable the governments to attain high values for their export sectors, improve the values of currently exported goods, increasing the role of services as a contributor to the national economy. Additionally, the policies should help the economies to increase the penetration into bigger and more profitable markets, and help in maintaining their competitive nature and mindset.

Taxes placed on commodities, both for local and international use, determine the profitability and success of the export endeavors of a country. Piermartini (2004) suggests the use of export taxes in the improvement of the terms of trade. The improvement will help in smoothening the earnings from exports, improve diversification of production, and setting up the manufacturing sector as a way of alleviating poverty and redistribution of wealth back to society. Therefore, if the taxation system in the US is favorable to the exportation of weapons to the US, then the economy of the US will experience significant growth, and the population will have more wealth as a result. Also, reduced taxes will mean that Saudi Arabia will have more money to demand more weapons from the US.

Due to global competition, national policies have opted to become more perfectionist and detailed in nature. Also, unfair competition from competitors has made economies opt for the imposition of taxes on international companies that have set up in their countries to ensure that the mother countries of the companies do not benefit unfairly from their trade. Leo and Deng (2019) also mention the imposition of stringent environmental laws that are meant to keep environmental damage on the minimum, while also keeping competition fair. Therefore, if Saudi Arabia sets up policies that would give rise to the internal production of weapons instead of importing them from the US, it would mean that they save on the extra amounts that they would have spent in the course of the trade. Also, this would mean that the US would have fewer profits since their biggest partner will have pulled out of their long-standing deal.

Bi lateral Relationship and the Export of Weapons between the Two Countries

Official relations between Saudi Arabia and the US began in the 1940s, and the US administrations over the years have termed the Saudi Kingdom as an essential partner. Arms sales and other related security co-operations between the US and Saudi Arabia are conducted under the supervision of both the Congress and the Congressional opposition (Congressional Research Service, 2020). Consequently, the executive branch of the US government has made Congress aware of over \$139 Billion worth of military sales proposals since 2009. There have been successfully concluded arms

sales of \$76 billion between the US and Saudi Arabia between 2009 and the 2017 financial years (Congressional Research Service, 2020). This being the case, it can be conclusively agreed that the US and Saudi Arabia have a successful business relationship as far as the export of arms is concerned.

Further, the ongoing business dealings between the US and Saudi Arabia on the export of oil to the US means that the relationship can only get stronger. This being so, the exportation of weapons between the two countries means that the two nations continually seek to provide positive working environments on which the dealings can prosper and increase the volumes of weapons exchanged between the two countries. Finally, it is correct to assume that when countries have a good relationship between themselves, then the possibility of business dealings between the two nations will be assured. However, countries that have tension or bad relationships between them experience adverse working conditions that mean they will not provide positive working environments for each other, and this will finally result in little or no trade happening between the two economies.

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